

Implementation of water-soluble cyclodextrin-based polymers in biomedical applications: how far are we?

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Abstract

Cyclodextrin-based polymers can be prepared starting from the naturally occurring monomers following green and low-cost procedures. They can be selectively derivatized pre- or post-polymerization allowing to fine-tune functionalities of *ad hoc* customized polymers. Preparation nowadays has reached the 100 g scale thanks also to the interest of industries in these extremely versatile compounds. During the last 15 years these macromolecules have been the object of intense investigations in view of possible biomedical applications as the ultimate goal and large amounts of scientific data are now available. Compared to their monomeric models, already used in the formulation of various therapeutic agents, they display superior behavior in terms of their solubility in water and solubilizing power towards drugs incompatible with biological fluids. Moreover, they allow the combination of more than one type of therapeutic agent in the polymeric system. In this review we provide a complete state-of-the-art on the knowledge and potentialities of water-soluble cyclodextrin-based polymers as therapeutic agents as well as carrier systems for different types of therapeutics to implement combination therapy. Finally, we give a perspective on their assets for innovation in disease treatment as well as their limits that still need to be addressed.

1. Introduction

1.1 Cyclodextrins at first sight

Cyclodextrins (CyDs) are water soluble, biocompatible macrocyclic oligosaccharides, made of α -D-glucopyranose units joined by $\alpha(1-4)$ linkages (**Figure 1a**).¹⁻² These natural macrocycles were discovered more than a century ago and they are obtained from starch by enzymatic degradation in the presence of amylases such as cyclodextrin glycosyltransferases.³⁻⁴ The most studied CyDs present 6, 7 or 8 glucose units and they are referred to as α , β and γ CyD, respectively (**Figure 1c**). These three types of CyDs share an overall shape of a truncated cone with the height of a glucose-molecule, whereas the number of glucopyranose units determines the size of the cavity (**Figure 1b-c**).⁵ This cavity is known for its slightly hydrophobic character given by the C-H bonds pointing towards the inner side of the ring, while the external faces are more hydrophilic, thanks to the presence of free hydroxy groups (**Figure 1b**).⁶ CyDs are able to form inclusion complexes with a wide variety of compounds with the latter fitting in the cavity entirely or partially. A large number of CyD

derivatives prepared exploiting the chemical reactivity of the hydroxy groups in positions 2, 3 and 6 of the glucose units are nowadays available⁷ and can be roughly divided into 3 categories:

- *Hydrophilic CyDs*: e.g., 2-hydroxypropyl- β CyD (HP β CyD);
- *Hydrophobic CyDs*: e.g., 2,3,6-tri-*O*-acetyl- β CyD or 6-*O*-*tert*-butyldimethylsilyl- β CyD
- *Ionizable CyDs*: e.g., sulfobutyl ether- β CyD (SBE β CyD) and amino-substituted CyDs.

Figure 1. Structure and dimensions of α , β and γ CyDs.

These derivatives can be mono-, randomly or fully substituted with either one or more functional groups, making them a very versatile substrate with unique properties.⁸ CyDs and their derivatives have been studied for 130 years (first CyD-related publication was from 1891) and nowadays a large number of technologies based on CyDs are available. We find them in different fields of applications concerning the formulation of pharmaceutical active substances, analytical separations, food and cosmetic additives, agricultural treatments, textile and environmental technologies, water decontamination, etc.^{3-4, 9-14}

In the field of biomedical applications and in particular drug development, CyDs received considerable attention thanks to their adequate safety profile and ability to host lipophilic drugs in their hydrophobic cavity.^{1, 15-17} Indeed, a very large number of drugs suffer from insolubility in physiological fluids because of their hydrophobic nature and induce severe side effects caused by the high drug doses required for optimizing the unfavorable pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic profiles. In this context, CyDs represent one of the most valuable tools to alter drug features, such as their pharmacokinetic and -dynamic profile, making them more patient (thus treatment) compliant. The encapsulation of a drug-guest into the cavity of a CyD-host can afford several advantages compared to the administration of the drug alone such as enhanced drug

solubility in physiological fluids, improved shelf life, enhanced bioavailability, better pharmacokinetics and -dynamics, reduced adverse side effects and so on.¹⁵ Most importantly, some CyDs are now approved by several food and drug agencies and used in drug formulations as well as cosmetics and food preparations (**Table 1**).^{10, 15, 18-19}

Table 1. Situation of the legislation regarding monomeric CyDs in 2021.¹⁰

CyDs	Food			Pharmacopoeia Monographs		
	US	Europe	Japan	US	Europe	Japan
α CyD	GRAS ^a	Novel Food	Natural product	Yes	Yes	Yes
β CyD	GRAS ^a	Food additive	Natural product	Yes	Yes	Yes
γ CyD	GRAS ^a	Pending	Natural product	In progress	In progress	Yes
HP β CyD				Yes	Yes	-
SBE β CyD				Yes	Yes	-

^a GRAS: Generally Recognized As Safe

solubility even though suitable tailoring of the ring can afford monomeric CyDs with highly improved solubility profile (**Table 2**).

Table 2. Aqueous solubility of different natural and derivatized CyDs.¹

	Substituent on the O atoms at positions 2, 3, 6	DS ^a	Solubility, mg/mL, 25 °C	Log P _{o/w}
Natural CyDs				
α CyD	-H	-	130	-13
β CyD	-H	-	18.5	-14
γ CyD	-H	-	249	-17
Modified CyDs				
HP β CyD	-CH ₂ -CHOH-CH ₃	4,6	>500	-11
SBE β CyD	-(CH ₂) ₄ -SO ₃ Na	6,3	>500	< -10
RM β CyD	-CH ₃	12,6	>500	-6
HP γ CyD	-CH ₂ -CHOH-CH ₃	4,8	>500	-13
Polymeric CyDs				
EPI-p β CyD ^b	-(CH ₂ -CHOH-CH ₂) _n -	8,5	>500	~-10

^aDS: degree of substitution. *i.e.* number of substituents per CyD unit; note that for some modified CyDs the value can somewhat change depending on the manufacturer;

^b CycloLab Product information: calculated from the CyD content determined by NMR.

1.2 Aim of this review

Monomeric CyDs were deeply explored and the most frequently used CyDs for commercial drug delivery formulations are β CyD, HP β CyD, SBE β CyD and α CyD.^{14-15, 20} Interestingly, one Covid-19 drug formulation (Veklury[®]) recently approved by US FDA actually exploits SBE β CyD to solubilize the API.²¹ A limit however to the practical use of the monomeric, natural CyDs is their aqueous

In the field of biomedical applications, the interest has gone well beyond the CyD monomers and their derivatives and scientists have been investigating composite systems incorporating various CyDs. During the last two decades with the advent of nanomedicine, a booming field holding a lot of promises, various CyD-based nanoassemblies, loading drugs *via* non covalent interactions²²⁻²⁴ or labile covalent bonds²⁵⁻²⁸ have been synthesized and proposed as delivery platforms and some have been considered for preclinical studies and the first Phase 2 clinical trial is going on.^{25, 29-30} The CyD-based nanoassemblies can be divided into various categories and recent literature refers to them in comprehensive reviews: CyD-decorated metal³¹ and mesoporous silica nanoparticles,³²⁻³³ star-shaped CyDs,³⁴⁻³⁸ self-assembled amphiphilic CyDs³⁹⁻⁴⁰ and CyD-grafted polymers.⁴¹ The latter polymers are very popular and often consist in biocompatible polymers made of chitosan, alginate, PEG, PGA, PLGA, PEI, and so on, modified with CyDs.⁴²⁻⁴³ CyD monomers have been i) grafted as host for hydrophobic guests in the side chain of preexisting polymers, ii) threaded with linear polymers to form rotaxanes and iii) used as capping molecule at the polymer end. Also, co-polymers have been widely investigated with CyD units grafted to one polymer backbone. Several researchers were attracted by the self-assembly of two different polymers with one linking CyDs and the other bearing molecules with high CyD cavity affinity such as adamantyl derivatives.⁴⁴ Some nice reviews collect information on CyD-based mixed polymeric materials used for drug delivery^{23, 45-49} and others describe the evolution in the preparation of these materials for biomedical applications.⁵⁰⁻⁵¹ Nowadays, the versatility of CyD-based nanoassemblies results in the description of a wide assortment of materials. In spite of the large number of systems described we miss streamlined translation of acquired knowledge to pharmaceutical exploitation and clinical applications mainly due to the fact that there is a huge gap between the design of the CyD-based therapeutic systems and their exploitation potential. Some of the aspects that up to now have been little addressed by the scientific community at the early design stage of CyD-based nanoassemblies are (i) the potential for production upscaling at affordable costs selecting, for example, low-cost and/or biocompatible reagents, (ii) selection of preparation protocols that can assure reproducibility of different production batches as well as sustainability thanks to circular economy production processes, identification of analytical methods that guarantee the product critical quality attributes, etc.^{48, 52} These are just few examples of aspects that are of fundamental importance for translation of knowledge that further requires effective communication between scientific community and all stakeholders from the private and clinical settings. The latter topic is discussed more deeply in chapter 6 for the CyD-based polymers.

In this context we narrow the focus of this review considering CyD-based polymers (pCyDs) bearing three main characteristics:

- **Aqueous solubility:** in order to target biomedical applications, this is a mandatory feature. Interestingly, dissolution of the polymers in water can afford significantly higher CyD concentration compared to the native CyDs in their monomeric form which is an obvious advantage in view of drug solubilization.
- **CyDs as main structural building block** of the polymer;
- Self-organisation in **small nanoparticles** of the polymers obtained upon reaction of a crosslinking agent in the presence of the monomeric CyDs.

Some of these pCyDs started to be produced already from the late 1980s and the first interesting applications in the pharmaceutical field were compiled in an early review by E. Fenyvesi in 1988.⁵³

Since then large amounts of new information have been collected and in this review, we will give a complete and up to date (31/12/2021) overview of the results obtained for all water-soluble pCyDs. In particular, in chapter 2 we discuss all information available on the synthetic strategies exploited up to now to prepare the water-soluble CyD-based polymers for biomedical applications. Chapter 3 deals with the intrinsic therapeutic activity of CyDs focusing both on monomers and pCyDs and collects the results published that shed light on the high potential of these compounds in neurodegenerative, inflammatory and infectious diseases and cancer. Chapter 4 concerns the CyD polymers as delivery systems of single or multiple therapeutic agents for various diseases and chapter 5 highlights the achievements for light-activated therapeutic systems obtained with pCyDs. The last chapter gives a perspective on their future industrial upgrade and translation potential to pharma industries and clinics. Noticeably, a large amount of scientific data has been obtained in the frame of EU funded research projects involving international consortia with private partners that were strongly exploitation-oriented.

2. Synthetic strategy design: importance of the crosslinking agent

Today, pCyDs are obtained following several approaches. Thanks to the great versatility of the CyDs building blocks, a variety of methodologies has been applied to the preparation of pCyDs and many of these were compiled and deepened in a comprehensive work of M.A. Przybyla *et al.*⁵⁴ focusing on the diverse chemistries that can be applied to the functionalization and thus polymerization of CyDs.

Among all the possible procedures, polycondensation in the presence of a bifunctional agent, called also crosslinking agent, and an alkylating agent, if needed to insert specific functionalities, has become very popular (**Figure 2**). It allows to produce in a convenient manner water-soluble polymers as well as water-insoluble hydrogels by rigorously controlling the initial concentration and molar ratio of crosslinking agent and CyD in the mixture as well as the reaction time and temperature.⁵⁵

Figure 2. Cartoon representation of a CyD-based polymer (pCyD) and chemical structures of most relevant crosslinking and alkylating agents described in this section.

In the following section, we will describe the most valuable synthetic approaches for the preparation by polycondensation of water-soluble pCyDs. Most importantly, as one of the strengths of the CyD building block is represented by its ability to host a guest in the hydrophobic cavity, the preparation protocol must guarantee accessibility of this cavity that can be hampered if large numbers of bridging units are introduced to the upper and/or lower rim. The pCyD systems will be grouped according to the crosslinking agent used i.e., epichlorohydrin, polycarboxylic acids, polyanhydride or others (**Table 3**). The physico-chemical properties of the obtained materials (i.e., charges due to ionizable groups, molecular weight (MW), aqueous solubility, *etc.*) will be deepened with respect to each specific case, since they vary according to the selected reagents and reaction conditions.

Table 3. Main classes of pCyDs discussed in this section.

CyD building block	Crosslinking agent ^a	Alkylating agent	Polymer Label	Reference	Overall charge
β CyD	EPI	-	EPI-p β CyD	54-59	Neutral
β CyD	EPI	Glycidyltrimethylammonium chloride <i>Quaternary ammonium moieties</i>	QA-EPI-p β CD	65	Positive
β CyD	EPI	Choline chloride <i>Quaternary ammonium moieties</i>	CC-EPI-p β CD	62	
β CyD	EPI	1,4-Butane sultone <i>Sulfobutyl ether moieties</i>	SBE-EPI-p β CyD	65	Negative
Carboxymethyl-(CM)- β CyD	EPI	Sodium chloroacetate <i>Carboxymethyl moieties</i>	EPI-CMp β CyD	64	
β CyD	CTR	-	CTR-p β CyD	66	
β CyD	PMDA	-	PMDA-p β CyD	70	
β CyD	MA	-	MA-p β CyD	74-75	
β CyD	PA	-	PA-p β CyD	74-75	
β CyD	NPA	-	NPA-p β CyD	74-75	

^a the acronym is described in figure 2 with the chemical structure and name.

2.1 Epichlorohydrin (EPI)

Epichlorohydrin (EPI) is the most widely used crosslinking agent in the synthesis of pCyDs. It allows to reach a CyD content up to 70% w/w, with relatively high molecular weight.⁵⁵⁻⁵⁸ EPI was the agent used in the first synthesis of pCyDs, dated back to the 1960s by J. Solms and R. H. Egli and refined by N. Wiedenhof *et al.*⁵⁹⁻⁶⁰ In these procedures, for the first time, EPI was used as crosslinking agent for the polymerization of a mixture of α , β and γ CyDs or selectively for α or β CyDs, respectively. The polymerization was achieved by heating at 80 °C for 5 h the solution in aqueous basic conditions (NaOH 30%).

Polycondensation between EPI and CyDs takes place, inevitably, on different functionalities of the substrates at the same time (**Figure 3**), generating a hyperbranched polymer composed of mono- or poly-glyceryl bridges connecting different CyD-units and ending dihydroxypropyl side chains. Thus, it was not trivial to parametrize the reaction conditions in order to obtain repeatable reactions and, above all, materials with reproducible physico-chemical characteristics.

Figure 3. Schematic representation of the simultaneous reaction steps happening during the polycondensation of EPI with CyDs in alkaline aqueous environment.

In 1997, E. Renard *et al.*⁵⁵ reported a first detailed analysis of the synthesis of a pCyD obtained by reacting β CyD with EPI (EPI-p β CyD) in which they optimized the reaction parameters in order to achieve water-soluble polymers in a controlled manner. They studied systematically the synthetic procedure keeping constant the size of the reaction vessel, the speed of the stirrer and the volume of the reaction mixture in order to minimize empirical variations. At 30 °C, they isolated soluble polymers when using molar ratios EPI: β CyD < 7 (yields \approx 80%), while for EPI: β CyD molar ratios in the range 7-15 also insoluble/gel materials were observed. At EPI: β CyD molar ratio = 3, the outcome of the reaction did not appear to be affected by temperature, however, the reaction rate indeed decreased while heating (tested up to 90 °C). Last, at EPI: β CyD molar ratio = 10 the NaOH concentration effect was explored and was found to influence the reaction rate as well as the ratio between each component in the EPI-p β CyD product and the average degree of substitution (DS, *ie.* Number of substituents per CyD unit). Overall, at lower NaOH concentration reaction rate increases and mostly soluble products are obtained with a EPI: β CyD molar ratio in the polymer similar to the monomers added in the reaction mixture, while at higher NaOH concentration the gelation point can be easily reached if the reaction is not quenched before. As confirmed by ¹³C NMR spectroscopy, substitution takes place at any of the three available positions on the two sides of the cavity, *ie.* the hydroxy groups on C-2, C-3 and C-6.⁶¹ Thus, the 2-hydroxypropyl ether segments can be attached on both sides of the cavity enabling each rim to be accessible for the link with another β CyD. ¹H NMR spectroscopy assessed that, when the average DS < 10, the end product is always soluble, while for DS > 12, the polycondensation gives rise to insoluble products. Size exclusion chromatography (SEC) was carried out to evaluate the molecular weight (MW) distribution of these compounds by refractive index measurements using pullulan samples as standards. Preparative SEC combined with refractive index measurements and low-angle laser light scattering was used to measure the average MW of different polymer fractions. They found the reaction conditions, in particular EPI: β CyD molar ratio and reaction time, strongly influenced the average MW of the polymers. The above-mentioned work⁵⁵ highlighted important milestones regarding the synthesis of neutral EPI-p β CyDs even though the size exclusion chromatography used to evaluate the MW of these compounds has been updated during the decades. Nowadays, more precise and reliable analytical techniques, namely dynamic and static light scattering (DLS and SLS), have been developed and tuned on this specific case:⁶² CycloLab *Ltd.* Commercializes α , β and γ CyD derivatives of water-soluble EPI-pCyDs with MW range of 20 000 – 260 000 g/mol. Renard *et al.* did not tackle the problem of CyD cavity accessibility in their first work focusing on the control of the MW of the

polymer and its solubility in water. While they established that the reaction can occur on both rims, the degree of substitution is expected to affect CyD cavity access and has been explored in some later works.

Using a one-pot approach, J. Li *et al.* introduced choline chloride (CC) in the EPI/ β CyD mixture to add a positive charge on the bulk EPI-p β CyD.⁶³ The reaction was performed with different molar ratios β CyD:EPI:CC in order to achieve oligomers (CC-EPI-p β CD) with various amounts of bridging units as well as varying cationic charge densities and thus increased water-solubility. Gel permeation chromatography was used for MW analysis using pullulan standards. The authors report on the number average MW (M_n) ranging from 2600 to 5400 g/mol and MW distribution depending both on the β CyD:EPI:CC molar ratio. One of the advantages of this strategy compared to the previously described multi-step approach is to achieve the introduction of permanently positive charges in one single step; nevertheless, the location of the cationic groups in the polymeric matrix is completely random and in-depth structural characterization becomes more challenging.

Despite the unfavorable safety profile, EPI is still today the most extensively used crosslinking agent for the synthesis of water-soluble pCyDs due to the high reactivity, commercial availability and low price. These polymers are hyperbranched 3D networks obtained according to the reaction schemes shown in Figure 3, and are sometimes referred to as crosslinked polymers even though the latter term is often used to indicate water-insoluble, swelling polymers. It is worth to mention that water-insoluble crosslinked pCyDs can also be prepared with EPI by slightly modifying the reaction conditions (i.e., concentration of CyDs, EPI: β CyD molar ratio, amount of base, reaction time, *etc.*). These polymers are particularly interesting for environmental applications, nevertheless, they are out of the scope of this review and will not be investigated further.⁶⁴ Being the polycondensation of EPI and CyDs as straightforward as selective and tunable, the EPI-pCyDs have been subjected to a number of further modifications affording materials with additional features, i.e., net charges, optical properties, *etc.* These modifications could be achieved following different strategies as described by M. Malanga *et al.*⁶⁵ and schematized in **Figure 4**:

- Post-polycondensation functionalization;
- Pre-polycondensation functionalization;
- Sequential polycondensation and functionalization.

Post-polycondensation functionalization: *introduction of functional groups performed after the formation of the polymer.* Exploiting well-known pathways to selectively modify CyD-monomers, a versatile strategy was developed for the addition of protonable amino groups (thus positive charges) and the subsequent introduction of a fluorescent tag on water-soluble EPI-p β CyDs (Figure 4). After the EPI-p β CyD was prepared, one amino moiety per CyD unit (0.5-2% of the CyD population) was added regioselectively on the primary rim of the CyDs. Then, rhodamine B isothiocyanate (RBITC) was coupled with $96 \pm 4\%$ of the amino groups as confirmed by UV-Vis spectroscopy and capillary electrophoresis (CE) measurements, leaving virtually no free amino groups on the bulk polymer, thus still neutral.⁶⁵

In a similar manner, methylation of EPI-p β CyD with CH₃I could be performed in order to tune solubility and complex formation ability of the end product. As the process is not selective, the crosslinking agent is methylated as well. Thus, for the correct NMR evaluation of the amount of inserted methyl groups, the CyD content of EPI-p β CyD ($\approx 70\%$) was taken into consideration, resulting in ~ 5.6 methyl moieties per CyD unit. Both the methylation and the polycondensation

affect preferably the secondary -OH groups, leaving the primary -OHs accessible for the introduction of an anchoring group such as a tosyl unit to link a like 4-methyl-7-hydroxy-coumarin.⁶⁵

Figure 4. Schematic representation of the pre- and post-polycondensation strategies for the functionalization of EPI-p β CyD.⁶⁵

Pre-polycondensation functionalization: introduction of functional groups in the CyD-monomers before the formation of the polymer. While in the previous approach, EPI can interact with the maximum number of hydroxy groups available per CyD ring, in the pre-polycondensation functionalization strategy, EPI reacts with a modified CyD, meaning that a portion of hydroxy groups is not available, resulting in lower DS for the crosslinking glyceryl bridges (Figure 4, above). As reported again by M. Malanga *et al.* the polycondensation of EPI with 6-monoazido-6-monodeoxy- β CyD monomers leads to a strong simplification for the characterization of the obtained polymer since each CyD unit bears only one azido moiety at the primary side.⁶⁵ By ¹H NMR evaluation, the N₃ content was calculated to be ~2.4% w/w. Reduction of the azido moieties to amino groups and labeling of the resulting cationic polymer with nitrobenzofurazan (NBF), a green dye, was then successfully achieved by nucleophilic substitution. NBF shows fluorescence only when linked to the amino moieties, facilitating the TLC monitoring of the reaction. Following this approach, anionic, carboxymethyl- β CyD polymers (EPI-pCM β CyD) were prepared. The functionalization of β CyD with sodium chloroacetate was performed in alkaline solution to get CM β CyD. Further addition of NaOH ensures the needed equimolar quantity related to EPI, which is added at the end.

Sequential polycondensation and functionalization: introduction of different functional groups in the polymer. H. Thomsen *et al.* used this strategy in order to prepare a set of rhodamine-labeled β CyD polymers (Rho-EPI-p β CyD) bearing simultaneously a fluorophore and ionizable groups.⁶⁶ While the rhodaminy groups were incorporated pre-polycondensation, the charged groups were inserted after the polycondensation reaction by reacting EPI with a mixture of unlabeled β CyD and Rho-labeled β CyD. Anionic sulfobutylether and cationic quaternary ammonium polymers (Rho-SBE-EPI-p β CyD and Rho-QA-EPI-p β CD, respectively) were prepared by adding 1,4-butane sultone (molar ratio 6:1 with respect to β CyD, where β CyD content is determined by ¹H NMR) or glycidyltrimethylammonium chloride (molar ratio 4:1 with respect to β CyD, where β CyD content is determined by ¹H NMR), respectively, as alkylating agents in the reaction mixtures. Interestingly, the measured average size was found larger for the charged particles probably due to the increased electrostatic repulsion: DLS measurements showed that the same MW of 50 000 g/mol corresponds

to approximately 5 nm average size in the case of Rho-EPI-p β CyD, 11,4 nm for Rho-SBE-EPI-p β CyD and 15,7 nm for Rho-QA-EPI-p β CD.

Interestingly, the functionalization strategies described above could be applied also to pCyDs prepared with agents other than EPI described in the following sections.

2.2 Polycarboxylic acids (PCAs)

The use of crosslinking agents other than EPI came across more recently. In the late 1990s and beginning of 2000s, the group of B. Martel published⁶⁷ and patented⁶⁸ a new synthesis for water-soluble polymers by polycondensation of CyDs and polycarboxylic acids (PCAs) to replace EPI, a toxic and carcinogen compound. They proposed a greener method involving non-toxic reagents (i.e., PCAs) and catalysts (i.e., phosphate salts) resulting in polymers (PCA-pCyDs) with biodegradable ester linkages. Difunctional carboxylic acids were tested (e.g., oxalic, malonic, glutaric acids) without success, suggesting that the crosslinking agents need at least three carboxylic groups. Therefore, 1,2,3,4-butanetetracarboxylic acid (BTCA), poly(acrylic acid) (PAA; average MW = 2000 g/mol) and, above all, citric acid (CTR) were used in combination with native β CyD, as well as with α CyD, γ CyD, 2-hydroxypropyl- β CyD (HP β CyD) and randomly methylated- β CyD. The latter was not further explored due to the low yields of soluble polymer.

The NaH₂PO₄, CyDs and PCAs were solubilized in water in a 2,2:1:5 molar ratio (**Figure 5**, respective concentrations of 0,2, 0,09, and 0,45 M, for the synthesis of CTR-p γ CyDs). After concentration, the dried mixtures were heated up to 140 - 170 °C under reduced pressure in order to favor the complete removal of water formed by the polycondensation reaction. These conditions favor the ester formation and the consequent improvement in the yield of the insoluble fractions (up to 90%), while mainly soluble gel products were obtained at T < 150 °C with a maximum yield of 30% when vacuum was applied. The nature of the CyD derivative was found to influence the overall yield of the reaction. For example, the soluble fractions obtained with CTR-pCyDs were in the range of 17% - 33% (β CyD). The same reaction (T = 140 °C) performed with BTCA as more reactive crosslinking agent brought about an increased gelation of the system. All the synthesized CTR-pCyDs showed excellent water solubility (> 1 g/100 mL at 25 °C) compared to monomeric CyDs (for β CyD = 1,8 g/100 mL at 25 °C). SEC combined with refractive index measurements revealed a high MW fraction with a peak MW of approximately 100 000 g/mol. Interestingly, the yield of water-soluble CTR-p β CyD fraction increases up to a molar ratio CyD:CTR = 1:3 (max yield \approx 30%), while it decreases at higher values. The yield of the insoluble fractions, instead, increases virtually linearly with the CyD:CTR molar ratio (max yield \approx 90%). Since many esterifiable groups (namely 21 hydroxy groups) are present on each β CyD unit, an increased molar ratio between CyDs and PCAs induces a more cross-linked end product which translate into an increase of gel/insoluble fraction to the detriment of the soluble one.

Figure 5. Schematic representation of the polycondensation procedure for the synthesis of CTR-pyCyDs ($T = 140\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, cat. = NaH_2PO_4).⁶⁷

The aforementioned synthesis of water-soluble CTR-pCyDs was slightly improved by the work of M. Skiba and M. Lahiani-Skiba.⁶⁹ They managed to increase the yield of the soluble fraction up to 40% (w/w) by performing the polycondensation reaction at $150\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 1 h, obtaining a weight average MW of the polymer threefold higher than the ones described in ref 68, namely $240\ 000\ \text{g/mol}$ ($M_n\ 30\ 000\ \text{g/mol}$), $272\ 000\ \text{g/mol}$ ($M_n\ 44\ 200\ \text{g/mol}$) and $310\ 000\ \text{g/mol}$ ($M_n\ 43\ 000\ \text{g/mol}$) for CTR- α CyD, CTR- β CyD and CTR- γ CyD, respectively, determined by SEC coupled to Multiangle Laser-light Scattering. The same group also synthesized a mixed CTR- $\alpha\beta$ CyD using the same polycondensation procedure.⁷⁰

It is worth to mention that, with this procedure, it is very difficult to avoid gel formation, especially because it forecasts to heat a solid material, disabling a homogeneous stirring of the mixture. This approach makes difficult to control the batch-to-batch reproducibility and a quite challenging industrial upscale. Moreover, the high temperature causes degradation and side-reactions to occur, often leading to yellowish compounds which might need charcoal treatment. In the case of EPI- β CyDs, instead, the reaction is performed in solution and it allows a much easier control, especially over the gel formation.

2.3 Polyhydrides

Anhydrides could be exploited as crosslinking agents for the preparation of CyD-based polymers, eventually bearing an overall negative charge at physiological conditions for the presence of residual carboxylic acid moieties. F. Trotta *et al.* described the preparation in 3 h and at r.t. of β CyDs in DMSO in the presence of catalytic amount of triethylamine (TEA) and a huge excess of pyromellitic dianhydride (PMDA) (Figure 2).⁷¹ The synthesized PMDA- β CyDs showed high water solubility ($800\ \text{mg/mL}$) over a wide pH range and ultrafiltration showed two main fractions: 48% with $3000 < \text{MW} < 10\ 000\ \text{g/mol}$ and 43.5% with $\text{MW} > 30\ 000\ \text{g/mol}$. SEC experiments of the latter fraction revealed an average MW of $42\ 000\ \text{g/mol}$ and M_n of $37\ 000\ \text{g/mol}$. The same group applied very similar procedures to prepare water-insoluble materials (i.e., CyD-nanosponges) from either PMDA, carbonyldiimidazole (CDI) or ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA), and they found that modulating the PMDA: CyD ratio to 10:1 or 12:1, the end polymers are highly water-soluble.⁷² An adapted procedure was used by the same group⁷³ to prepare the PMDA- α CyD analogues and by the group of H. Cabral-Marques in order to prepare polymeric derivatives of RM β CyD and HP β CyDs, respectively.⁷⁴

Polymerization of β CyD with maleic anhydride (MA) and phthalic or 3-nitrophthalic anhydrides (PA or NPA) was performed in the presence of NaH.⁷⁵⁻⁷⁶ In the first case, water-soluble MA- β CyDs could be obtained at $60\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C} < T < 100\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ with a molar ratio $\beta\text{CyD}:\text{NaH}:\text{MA} = 1:7:7$. High performance SEC

(HPSEC) with refractive index and multiangle laser-light scattering detectors highlighted an average MW between 78 000 and 88 000 g/mol after 12 h of reaction at 100 °C. However, after 24 h in the same conditions, the average MW became higher, 288-380 000 g/mol, leading to mostly insoluble materials. Also for the synthesis of PA-p β CyDs and NPA-p β CyDs, soluble fractions (MW \approx 100 000 g/mol) were mostly obtained at molar ratio β CyD:NaH:PA = 1:7:7 and 65 °C < T < 100 °C.

2.4 Other synthetic procedures of p β CyDs for biomedical applications

The protocols described above starting with mainly two building blocks, the CyD and the crosslinking agent, afforded hyperbranched CyD polymers under certain reaction conditions. Some groups reported on the preparation of linear polymers changing reagents as well as reaction conditions. In 2001, Davis' group synthesized linear cationic p β CyDs by condensation of a dicysteamine-appended β CyD monomer (A) with diimidate comonomers (B) of different length, in order to produce an ABAB polymer (**Figure 6a**).⁷⁷ Polymerization was achieved in aqueous Na₂CO₃ (0,5 M) solution, by mixing equimolar amounts of A and B at 25 °C for 15 h. The length of the comonomer B (from 4 to 8 methylene groups as spacers) was found to influence the polymerization: the yields were between 18% and 37%, while the polydispersity index, determined by SLS, showed values in the range 1,12-1,16. Moreover, the MW determined by SLS showed values between 5800 and 7600 g/mol, in good agreement with the ones obtained from the estimated end-group (carboxylic acid or amine) analysis, between 4600 and 6200 g/mol.

Figure 6. Chemical structures of a) the ABAB p β CyD obtained from M. Davis' group in water and in the presence of Na₂CO₃, at 25 °C for 15 h.⁷⁷ b) the linear p β CyD ORX-301 obtained by A. Kulkarni *et al.* with a "click" reaction at 60 °C for 24 h in water and in the presence of Cu(PPh₃)₃Br.⁷⁸

Another linear high MW polymer was synthesized in a more recent work by A. Kulkarni *et al.* who designed a degradable, prodrug version of a p β CyD (named by the authors ORX-301) by using a pre-condensation functionalization approach (**Figure 6b**).⁷⁸ A "click" reaction was performed in order to condense A,D-diazido- β CyD with a difunctionalized ketal linker at 60 °C for 24 h in DMF and in the

presence of $\text{Cu}(\text{PPh}_3)_3\text{Br}$. Gel permeation chromatography (GPC) in DMF showed a MW peak of $\sim 33\ 000$ g/mol and a polydispersity index (PDI) of 1,02. Some caution is recommended with this PDI value considering that the authors reported a MW peak implying a range of MWs observed for this system studied with gel permeation chromatography.

Using a similar approach, the very recent work of M. Zhang *et al.* aimed to synthesize water-soluble hyperbranched $\text{p}\beta\text{CyDs}$ *via* thiol-maleimide 'click' chemistry (actually, a Michael addition reaction) using exclusively modified βCyD building blocks.⁷⁹ By following a pre-polycondensation strategy, two complementary CyD-substrates, namely per-6-thiolated βCyD ($\beta\text{CyD-SH}$) and *N*-maleoyl alanine (AMI)-hydroxypropyl- βCyD (HPCyD-AMI) were synthesized and subsequently condensed in aqueous NaOH (0,04 M) by varying the molar ratio of the components and the reaction temperature. The obtained AMI-SH- $\text{p}\beta\text{CyDs}$ were all water soluble, showing both the average MW and polydispersity increasing with the temperature: 285 000 g/mol with PDI = 1,38 when the reaction was performed at 37 °C; and 411 000 g/mol with PDI = 1,88 when the reaction was performed at 80 °C. Even though the synthetic idea is interesting, the procedure is troublesome. A critical aspect of this original approach is that $\beta\text{CyD-SH}$ in alkaline conditions forms immediately intramolecular disulfide bridges, thus lowering the numbers of thiols accessible for the polycondensation. This emerges in the NMR spectra of the final compound, showing sharp peaks and not the characteristic broad signals like in a polymer. The Steglich reaction could have been further demonstrated by ^1H and ^{13}C NMR as well as MS.

3. Intrinsic therapeutic activity of pCyDs

For a long period CyDs have been considered as inactive ingredients of pharmaceutical formulations, but actually an increasing number of observations suggested that at least some CyD derivatives have intrinsic therapeutic effect that may be exploited in the treatment of various diseases.⁴ In most cases the activity has been attributed to the affinity of various CyDs for cholesterol and its derivatives as discussed in the following parts of this chapter. **Figure 7** shows an example of cholesterol complexes with two βCyD dimers reported by Anderson *et al* whose structure was determined by 2D ROESY NMR.⁸⁰

Figure 7. Schemes for a) butyl-linked ($\text{DS} \approx 8$) and b) triazole-linked ($\text{DS} \approx 3$) dimers of HP β CD ($\text{DS} \approx 4.6$, Table 2) complexing with cholesterol (crystal structure reference CCDC reference: [184885](#)). Data were derived from 2D ROESY NMR experiments in CD_3OD .⁸⁰ structure of c) cholesterol, d) 7-keto cholesterol and e) 27-hydroxycholesterol.

3.1 Neurodegenerative diseases

A most surprising discovery was that HP β CyD, the solubilizer of allopregalonone, was just as effective in increasing the lifespan of mice with Niemann Pick type C disease (NPC) as the drug formulation.⁸¹⁻⁸² Due to these effects and the high need of effective NPC treatment, HP β CyD was granted orphan drug designation by FDA and Phase 2b/3 clinical trials were started.⁸³⁻⁸⁴ HP β CyD activity is still not completely understood and has been attributed to cholesterol complexing ability of HP β CyD which can shuttle cholesterol out of the cell similarly to the NPC1 and NPC2 proteins. Comparing various CyDs including also α - and γ -derivatives with low affinity toward cholesterol a more complex mechanism based on interactions with various lipids, such as 27-hydroxycholesterol and sphingosine has been postulated.⁸⁵ As only a low concentration of HP β CyD can cross the blood-brain barrier (BBB),⁸⁶⁻⁹⁰ high doses (1500-2500 mg/kg) are applied intravenously to achieve brain therapeutic concentration with high risk of toxic effects, such as pulmonary and ototoxicity, or alternatively patient-unfriendly and invasive intrathecal or intracerebroventricular administrations are used with a lower dose.⁹¹ To reduce toxicity and improve pharmacokinetic properties and bioavailability, CyD based macromolecular systems have been developed.^{78, 92-93} Compared to monomer CyDs, pCyDs have the advantage of retarded renal clearance and sustained elimination thus increased blood circulation half-life that can set better conditions for the polymers to get through BBB via carrier-mediated transcytosis thanks to their larger size.⁹² A linear polymer prodrug (MW 33 000 g/mol) based on β CyD monomer units linked together by a short pH-degradable ketal linkage (ORX-301, see section 2.4) was found to circulate in the blood for a longer time than HP β CyD and penetrate through BBB following endocytotic engulfment resulting in increased lifespan of NPC mice.^{78, 94} A single dose of 800 mg/kg given subcutaneously to NPC mice delayed the onset and slowed the progression of ataxia. The improved bioavailability is attributed to the larger size. While HP β CyD is cleared within the first few hours, the polymer can be detected even after 48 h. In another approach, β CyD was coupled to poly(caprolactone) by benzoic imine groups then let to self-aggregate to form polymersome microparticles (1675 nm in average diameter) which are able to cross biological barriers, enter the cells via endocytosis and, after acidic cleavage at lysosomal pH, β CyD is released locally in the lysosome.⁹³

An EPI-pHP β CyD polymer with MW 19 300 g/mol with non-biodegradable ether linkages and hydrodynamic diameter of 6,5 nm showed an *in vivo* half-life 2,5 times longer than the monomer HP β CyD but the life span of Npc1^{-/-} mice did not increase due to limited brain delivery.⁹⁵ The authors of the study used magnetic resonance imaging-guided low intensity-pulsed focused ultrasound (MRIG-FUS) to transiently open the BBB for the polymer and increase its concentration in the brain. They concluded that the non-biodegradable ether linkages hindered tissue penetration.

CyDs have beneficial effects in other neurodegenerative diseases, like Alzheimer's, Parkinson's and Huntington's diseases.⁹⁶ The improved bioavailability and BBB-penetration of the pCyDs compared to monomer CyDs may represent a still unexplored advantage in these diseases, too.

3.2 Atherosclerosis

High blood cholesterol concentration is a main risk factor of atherosclerosis, the leading cause of death and disability worldwide. It is an inflammatory disease characterized by cholesterol accumulation and deposition of cholesterol crystals in atherosclerotic plaques in arteries. It was shown that HP β CyD treatment reduced atherogenesis and atherosclerotic plaque size via

solubilizing cholesterol crystals.⁹⁷⁻⁹⁸ In the search for derivatives of longer blood circulation time p β CyDs were also studied.⁹⁹ The half-life time in blood was measured for carboxymethyl-substituted β CyD and its polymer (CM-p β CyD); the CM group was necessary to couple the fluorescent dye for visualization via microscopy. Polymerization increased the blood half-life after i.v. injection to ApoE^{-/-} mice from 0,46 h to 26,8 h (58 times). The biodistribution studies showed that while the monomer was excreted through the kidney, the polymer was cleared in the liver. The polymer preferably accumulated in the plaques of dissected aortic tree providing 14 times higher CyD concentration in the plaques than the monomer.⁹⁹ The cholesterol removing capacity of EPI-p β CyD is only slightly lower than that of RAMEB, followed by EPI-CM-p β CyD > HP β CyD >> CM β CyD (Table 4).

Table 4. Removal of crystalline cholesterol from macrophages using 5 mM CyD solutions.⁹⁹

CyD-derivatives	pCyDs		CyD-monomers		
	EPI-p β CyD	EPI-pCM β CyD	RAMEB	HP β CyD	CM- β CyD
Cholesterol removal (%)	43	18	50	10	<2

Ex vivo culture of atherosclerotic plaques dissected from mice previously injected once with either HP β CyD or EPI-p β CyD at a dose of 1 g/kg showed that the polymer induced higher cholesterol efflux from plaques. The plaque area was decreased by about 40% by the polymer compared to 10% by HP β CyD treatment. EPI-p β CyD treatment did not changed significantly plasma, cholesterol and liver-associated enzyme levels and body weight was not altered either showing that it has no systemic toxicity. These results suggest that EPI-p β CyD can be used more efficiently for the treatment of atherosclerosis than HP β CyD. The mechanism was supposed to be based on removal of intracellular and extracellular cholesterol within plaques.⁹⁹

Other researchers found that the removal of toxic oxysterols, such as 7-ketocholesterol (7-KC) is the key target in the treatment of several age-related diseases such as atherosclerosis, macula degeneration, cancer etc.¹⁰⁰ 7-KC and some other oxysterols increase in abundance with age, some of them as 27-hydroxycholesterol (27-HC) can cross the BBB increasing the risk of such diseases. Recently, O'Connors group has published on CyD-dimers designed for the extraction of atherogenic 7-KC from cells and tissues (Figure 7).⁸⁰ As a next step the design and preparation of oligomers and polymers with specific affinity toward oxysterols are expected.

3.3 Viral infections

The cholesterol binding/complexing CyDs and CyD-derivatives are inhibitors of viral outbreak and viral infections. The effect against virus infection is based on the interaction of CyDs with the lipid envelope of the virus. The viral envelope consists of glycerophospholipids (phosphatidylcholine and phosphatidylethanolamine) and cholesterol.¹⁰¹ The first step of virus infection is docking on the lipid raft domains of the recipient cells and fusion of viral envelope with the lipid bilayer of the host cell. Viral envelope also protects the viral core, plays a role in virus attachment, and contributes to the stability of newly formed infectious viruses. Treating the virions by RAMEB, a cholesterol extracting agent, significantly reduced the infectivity of influenza virus in a dose-dependent manner.¹⁰² Removal of cholesterol can destroy the envelope structure of both influenza A virus and respiratory syncytial virus.¹⁰³

One of the possible applications of these observations is impregnating the face masks with a proper CyD having lipid-chelator properties which upon contact will remove the lipids, especially cholesterol from the viral envelope thus reducing its infectivity. In this optics, CyDs were fixed on different fabrics by various coupling agents, most preferably epichlorohydrin¹⁰⁴ and di- or polycarboxylic acids.¹⁰⁵⁻¹⁰⁶ The CTR-pCyD formed *in situ* around the fibers preserves the complex forming ability.¹⁰⁷ Enhanced CyD concentration can be achieved on the mask if a prepolymer, e.g., EPI-pCyD or CTR-pCyD containing several CyD units, is immobilized on the fabric.

3.4 Bacterial Infections

The groups of R. Gref and P. Brodin focused on the exploration of the intrinsic antibacterial activity of nanoparticles made of EPI-p β CyD.¹⁰⁸ Interestingly only EPI-p β CyD, but no EPI-p α CyD nor EPI-p γ CyD showed this effect suggesting that β CyD-specific interactions, e.g., with cholesterol, may be involved in the mechanism. The antituberculous effects were observed when EPI-p β CyD was administered pulmonary in mice (30 - 400 mg/kg of body weight) exposed to *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (Mtb). Lung mycobacterial load in Mtb-challenged mice was reduced in a dose dependent manner. EPI-p β CyD was preferentially accumulated in alveolar macrophages compared to interstitial macrophages, neutrophils, eosinophils, B-lymphocytes and T-cells. These effects were explained by the ability of p β CyD to interact with lipid components of cell membrane and disrupting cell surface lipid rafts and with this inhibiting docking of bacteria. Indeed, cholesterol was depleted from cell membrane and found distributed throughout the cytosol after the treatment. As a consequence, the colonization of macrophages by Mtb was reduced. This effect was proved also *in vivo*: the number of alveolar macrophages declined considerably to 25% due to apoptosis. On the other hand, EPI-p β CyD showed no genotoxicity and no significant pro-inflammatory effect. This intrinsic antibacterial effect is, however, not general; EPI-p β CyD was not effective against other bacterial pulmonary pathogens such as *Brucella abortus* and *Bordetella pertussis* (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Assessment of the effect of EPI-p β CyD on the lung mycobacterial load in Mtb-challenged mice. (A) BALB/c mice were anesthetized and i.n. inoculated with 10^5 CFU of Mtb H37Rv strain in 20 μ L of PBS. At days 7, 9, 11, 14, 16, and 18 postchallenge, mice received administrations of 50 μ L of various EPI-p β CyD concentrations via the e.t. route using a microsyringe that generated aerosolization directly into the lungs. At day 21 postchallenge, lungs were harvested for determination of bacterial burden by CFU counting. (B) Bacterial load at day 21 postchallenge after 6 inoculations of 50 μ L of different EPI-p β CyD concentrations by the e.t. route. (C) Comparison of the impact of EPI-p β CyD (6x50 μ L at 150 mg/mL) on Mtb pulmonary load administrated by the i.n. route or by the e.t. route after i.n. infection.

Symbols ** and *** denote $p < 0,01$ and $p < 0,001$, respectively.¹⁰⁸ Reprinted from ref. 106 with permission from American Chemical Society.

Modifying pCyDs with cationic groups may enlarge the plethora of bacterial infections to be treated: the positively charged polymer can attach to the negatively charged bacterial membrane by means of electrostatic interactions.¹⁰⁹ In addition, the positive charge may result in a slight intrinsic antibiotic effect. For instance, the antiseptic/preservative effect of quaternary β CyDs in ophthalmic formulations was demonstrated.¹¹⁰ The microparticles obtained by crosslinking CyD with isophorone diisocyanate and substituted with quaternary ammonium groups was effective against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*.

3.5 Cytotoxicity and hemolysis of pCyDs

In view of their therapeutic applications some groups addressed the issue of pCyD cytotoxicity and hemolytic ability. The cytotoxicity of CyDs depends mainly on their structure (cavity size, type, number and pattern of substituents, hydrophilic/amphiphilic character, etc.), the applied concentration and the time of exposure but also the type of cells, environment of the cells, such as the presence of serum lipids, and the density of the cells, can dramatically influence the cytotoxic effect.¹¹¹⁻¹¹² In the case of the pCyDs also other factors are expected to play a role such as the MW of the polymer. Up to now a detailed study of the effect of the polymer MW on organ uptake and accumulation/degradation is not available and most data actually concern cell studies. Native CyDs at high concentrations induce hemolysis of human erythrocytes due to interaction with the membrane components in the order of α CyD $>$ β CyD \gg γ CyD with phospholipids, β CyD $>$ γ CyD $>$ α CyD with cholesterol, and β CyD \gg γ CyD $>$ α CyD with proteins.¹¹³ These processes occurred without entry of CyDs into the membrane as shown by ¹⁴C-labeled β CyD. The hemolytic effects of EPI-p β CyD and its carboxymethyl analog EPI-pCM β CyD are much lower compared to β CyD (**Figure 9**).¹¹² No significant cytotoxicity and hemolytic activity were detected for EPI-p β CyD and its CM-derivative by Kim *et al.*, either.⁹⁹ The authors report improved pharmacokinetics and biodistribution of the polymers compared to the analogous monomers and ascribe these features to the larger size of the polymer organizing in nanoparticles with ~ 8 nm size helping the system to evade renal clearance. The quaternary ammonium β CyD polymer (QA-EPI-p β CyD) was non-toxic to both PC12 and Caco-2 cells, a neuronal (rat pheochromocytoma-derived cell) and an epithelial (human colorectal adenocarcinoma cell) type cell, respectively, at 5 mM and 60 min of exposure.¹¹⁴ The quaternary amino substituted polymer obtained by crosslinking β CyD with epichlorohydrin in the presence of choline chloride (CC-EPI-p β CyD) showed reduced hemolytic activity compared to β CyD: the higher the degree of crosslinking and substitution the lower the cytotoxicity was attributed to the reduced capability of binding cholesterol.⁶³

Figure 9. Hemolytic effects of β CyD (\bullet), EPI-p β CyD (\circ) and EPI-pCM β CyD (\bullet) on human erythrocytes in 10 mM isotonic buffer at pH 7.4 at 37 °C.¹¹²

Ethionamide		Antibiotic	EPI-pβCyD
Clofazimine		Antibiotic	SBE-EPI-pβCyD
Cyclosporine A		Immuno-suppressant	CTR-αβ-pCyD
Naproxen		Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory	CC-EPI-pβCD
Artemisinin		Antimalarial	EPI-pβCyD
Diclofenac		Anti-inflammatory	EPI-amino-pβCyD
Ebselen		Anti-HIV	EPI-pβCyD

4.1 Antitumorals

A very recent review focuses on *in vivo* tests for CyD-based delivery systems constituting several building blocks with the CyD being either grafted to a polymer, or part of a liposomal delivery vehicle for anticancer therapies.¹¹⁷ The first example of the use of a pCyDs as carrier for antitumorals was reported by the group of P. Couvreur. They prepared a nanogel mixing EPI-pβCyD with a lauryl-modified dextran polymer with the hydrophobic alkyl side chains hosted in the CyD cavities, thus favoring the supramolecular gel formation.¹¹⁸⁻¹¹⁹ Using EPI-pβCyD to dissolve tamoxifen (**Table 5**), a drug used in breast cancer treatment, they still obtained the gel upon mixing with lauryl-modified

dextran polymer. The gel loading the drug can be injected *in vivo* thanks to the weak non-covalent interactions keeping the two polymers together as well as affording a flexible nature to the gel (**Figure 10**). The EPI-p β CyD was able to dissolve high amounts of drug in water, up to 0,7 mM compared to 0,15 mM for β CyD, and *in vitro* release of the drug was obtained at 37 °C with the amount of released drug increasing linearly with time and reaching 11% after 4 days.¹¹⁸ Importantly, much higher amounts of β CyD could be dissolved in water as polymer (up to 100 mg/mL corresponding to 70 mg/mL of β CyD) compared to the monomeric β CyD having a limit of 17,5 mg/mL affording a rationale for the improved drug solubilization.

Figure 10. Self-assembling of lauryl-modified dextran and EPI-p β CyD affords hydrogels for the sustained delivery of hydrophobic drugs such as Tamoxifen.¹¹⁸

In a following publication the same group reported that mixing the two previous polymers in lower amounts allowed to obtain supramolecular nanoparticle assemblies with a dimension below 200 nm and size stability over 20 days.¹¹⁹⁻¹²⁰ The high molecular weight of EPI-p β CyD is one of the determining factors in the self-assembly process. Again, inclusion of the dextran hydrophobic alkyl chains in the molecular cavities of EPI-p β CyD demonstrated with ¹H NMR promoted nanoassembly formation leaving about 50% of the cavities empty. The unoccupied CyD units remained accessible for the inclusion of compounds of interest such as tamoxifen or benzophenone. In particular, the authors have shown inclusion of the model compound benzophenone in the CyD cavity with ¹H NMR and the displacement of the dextran alkyl chains in the cavity by the guest, a process not compromising the formation of the nanoassemblies.¹¹⁹ The nanoparticle assemblies loaded 100 μ g of tamoxifen per 100 mg of dried polymer which are sufficient for clinical application.¹¹⁹ The therapeutic benefit was counterbalanced by a moderate inflammatory reaction, attributed to the administration of NPs prepared using organic solvents. They further optimized the preparation procedure of the nanoassemblies and demonstrated that stable nanoassemblies could be obtained only in a very narrow range of experimental conditions and that the main parameters governing stability were the dextran substitution degree with alkyl chains, the nature of the alkyl chain, the molar mass (M_w) of the p β CyD, the weight ratios of the polymers in the mixture, and the absolute concentrations.¹²⁰⁻¹²² Freeze-drying was found to be a convenient method for the long-time storage of nanoassemblies. Moreover, sterilization of the nanoassemblies was possible and biocompatibility studies exploring intramuscular administration of the gels showed promising preliminary results in the view of their pharmaceutical application.¹²³ Finally, the entrapment of two hydrophobic molecules, tamoxifen and benzophenone, into self-assembling CyD-based nanogels was pursued to valorize the hypothesis of contemporary delivery of more than one therapeutic agent.⁵¹ The interactions of benzophenone and tamoxifen with alkylated dextran and p β CyD were investigated

using phase solubility studies, circular dichroism, and isothermal titration calorimetry. On basis of circular dichroism data, it was possible to hypothesize that both hydrophobic molecules were included into the CyD cavities of the p β CyD. Phase solubility studies suggested that they are also solubilized by dextran into its hydrophobic microdomains. These studies opened new possibilities of applications of the gels of nanoassemblies in the biomedical field. The same group also obtained NPs with a size of ca 100 nm mixing the p β CyD with benzophenone grafted dextran both dissolved in water in a microfluidic interaction chamber emphasizing the extremely green method to obtain the NPs.¹²⁴ The same system based on p β CyD and alkyl-chain modified dextran has been used also to successfully encapsulate a Gd(III) chelate modified with adamantyl exhibiting extremely high affinity for the hydrophobic β CyD cavity selected as a High-Relaxivity Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) contrast agent in an attempt to reduce the toxicity of these agents.¹²⁵

Subsequently others examined the encapsulation of one of the first antitumorals used, doxorubicin (DOX), (Table 5) a drug causing severe side effects.¹¹⁷ Two citric acid hyperbranched γ CyD oligomers (CTR-p γ CyD) with a MW of 21-33 000 g/mol and 10-15 γ CyD units per molecule were prepared and fully characterized. The non-covalent association of DOX with these macromolecules was investigated in neutral aqueous medium by means of circular dichroism, UV-Vis absorption and fluorescence. The binding constants are 1-2 orders of magnitude higher than those obtained for monomeric γ CyD. Confocal fluorescence imaging and spectral imaging showed a drug distribution within the MCF-7 cell line similar for CTR-p γ CyD complexed and free DOX.¹²⁶ The same authors evaluated also EPI-p β CyD for the encapsulation of DOX evidencing the ability of this polymer to disassemble dimers of the drug inside the NP.¹²⁶

The EPI-p β CyD polymer was evaluated as carrier for the delivery of RNA-cleaving DNase (DZ) an oligonucleotide of 10-23 bases with enzymatic activity which causes suppression of the c-Myc gene in MCF-7 cell line. Polymer and DZ spontaneously form complexes in buffer solutions. In the MCF-7 cell line a synergistic effect of the p β CyD/DZ complex and different concentration of DOX was reported.¹²⁷

Rohner *et al.* explored three different polymeric forms from the same γ CyD pre-polymer and found differences in polymer filling/refilling of the anti-cancer drug, DOX, over time. The ability in drug refilling of EPI-p γ CyD is not significantly affected by albumin and cholesterol, thus making in vivo CyD implants more attractive for future clinical investigations.¹²⁸

Terekhova *et al.* performed an accurate study on the difference in affinity of methotrexate (MTX), (Table 5) a drug with a broad spectrum of clinical activity including antitumoral, to the naturally occurring α -, β - and γ -CyDs as well as to the novel synthetic dimeric and polymeric β CyD.⁹⁴ They found that only β CyD and dimeric β CyD display a higher binding ability to MTX. Dimeric β CyD acts as a ditopic host forming rather stable 1:2 inclusion complexes with MTX. In contrast, MTX displays lower affinity for commercial EPI-p β CyD using the phase solubility approach in acidic medium. The thermodynamics and binding modes of CyDs with MTX were obtained and analyzed. The influence of buffer pH on the complexation process was considered. The binding affinity of β CyD to different ionized forms of MTX was examined using the capillary electrophoresis technique.

Some groups reported the use of crosslinked polyglycerol modified β CyD derivatives prepared with glycidol for delivery of docetaxel and epirubicin, the latter covalently attached to the branched β CyD oligomer. They obtained oligomers of very low MW in the 4000-5000 g/mol range with much higher water solubility compared to the β CyD monomer able to increase the selected drug solubility.

Docetaxel loading NPs with a size below 200 nm were obtained upon self-assembly with a slow drug release profile not presenting the initial burst.¹²⁹ In the case of epirubicin reaction of one ketyl group on the central quinone with the hydrazide functionality of the EPI-p β CyD afforded a covalent adduct. The dynamic hydrazone covalent bond was susceptible to pH and the drug uncaged more readily at pH 5.4. The epirubicin linking branched β CyD oligomer self-assembled in NPs with a size of about 50 nm.¹³⁰

4.2 Antibiotics

CyD polymers have been used also for the encapsulation of antibiotics. Martel *et al.* explored the combination of two polymers, one made of cyclodextrins, as antibiotic device. The aim of the study was the design of antibacterial electrospun nanofibers for hydrophobic drug release. They choose triclosan (Table 5), a poor-water soluble and broad-spectrum antimicrobial drug, with affinity for HP β CyD. An inclusion complex between a citric acid cross-linked HP β CyD polymer (CTR-pHP β CyD) and triclosan was formed in water; the obtained construct was then mixed with positively charged chitosan (Chit) and finally electrospun to yield nanofibers exploiting the opposite charges of the polymers. Nanofibers stability and swelling behavior in aqueous medium were pH and Chit:CTR-pHP β CyD weight ratio dependent. A high CTR-pHP β CyD content in addition to a thermal post treatment at 90 °C was necessary to reach nanofibers stability for 15 days at pH = 5.5. In dynamic conditions, a prolonged release of triclosan with a reduced burst effect was observed for the Chit-CTR-pHP β CyD triclosan polyelectrolyte complex. Following complete characterization of the drug loaded nanofibers, the antibacterial activity was tested against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* bacteria. Slow release of the drug in the medium caused a reduction in the bacteria population. Co-electrospinning of two oppositely charged polyelectrolytes leads to materials with improved stability in aqueous media; an additional advantage was the incorporation of an active molecule by complexation of the CyD cavities. The system based on the CTR-pHP β CyD displayed much better performance compared to the system prepared with equimolar amount of the HP β CyD monomer.¹³¹

Wankar *et al.* reported the use of a p β CyD for the encapsulation of ethionamide (ETH, Table 5).¹³² ETH is a second line drug for tuberculosis (TB) suffering from poor solubility in water and strong tendency to crystallize. The drug was incorporated in a molecular state avoiding crystallization even for long-term storage and obtaining a tenfold increased solubility up to 25 mM. The binding of ETH to EPI-p β CyD nanoparticles (EPI-p β CyD NPs) was investigated in neutral aqueous medium by means of solubility phase diagrams, circular dichroism (CD) and UV-Vis absorption and compared with the corresponding β CyD monomer. The binding constants and the absolute CD spectra of the drug complexes were determined by global analysis of multiwavelength data from spectroscopic titrations. ETH was found to be located not only in β CyD cavities, but also in confined microdomains inside the NPs. This double modality of complexation together with a slightly higher binding constant for p β CyD makes the utilization of EPI-p β CyD NPs preferable over the monomeric β CyDs. In view of *in vitro* experiments, fluorescein (FITC) labeled p β CyDs were investigated and the FITC labeling did not hamper the encapsulation of ETH. The p β CyD carrier was further investigated to co-encapsulate the drug ETH and a booster, organic molecules with limited water solubility.¹³³ Recently discovered “booster” molecules strongly increase the ETH efficacy, opening new perspectives in the treatment of drug-resistant TB. In view of the simultaneous delivery of ETH and a booster in the

lungs, ETH was co-encapsulated with 2 different boosters BDM41906 and BDM43266, within the p β CyD-NPs, overcoming the bottlenecks of ETH crystallization and booster limited water solubility (**Figure 11**). In case of booster BDM43266 the inclusion in EPI-p β CyD-NPs led to an increase of the apparent water solubility of ETH and BDM43266 of 10- and 90-fold, respectively. Competition studies of ETH and BDM43266 for the CyD cavities of p β CyD-NPs corroborated the fact that the drugs did not compete with each other. The drug/booster loaded NPs were passed through a Microsprayer[®], and each spray delivered a constant amount of both drugs and the NPs were totally recovered after passage through the Microsprayer[®].¹³³ The efficacy of the ETH formulation with booster BDM41906 was evaluated in TB infected macrophages using an automated confocal high-content screening platform, showing that the drugs maintained their activity after incorporation in NPs. The EPI-p β CyD-NPs suspension, administered directly into mouse lungs using a Microsprayer[®], was proved to be well-tolerated and led to a 3-log decrease of the pulmonary mycobacterial load after 6 administrations as compared to untreated mice. These studies pave the way for a future use of EPI-p β CyD-NPs for the pulmonary delivery of the [ETH:Booster] pair in TB chemotherapy.

Figure 11. Scheme for the contemporary loading of ETH and booster BDM43266 in EPI-p β CyD NPs; phase solubility diagrams of ETH and booster with increasing EPI-p β CyD or β CyD concentration expressed in β CyD molarity; phase solubility diagram of competition study adding booster before or after ETH loading (solvent: water). Reproduced from ref. 133 with permission from Elsevier.

In the frame of innovation in TB treatment Manet *et al.* reported the use of a negatively charged β CyD polymer (SBE-EPI-p β CyD) for the delivery of Clofazimine (CLZ, Figure 12), an antibiotic with a promising behavior against Gram-positive bacteria, including mycobacterium, to solubilize the drug in water and avoid its accumulation in fat tissues.¹³⁴ The oligomeric sulfonated carrier has a MW of 53 000 g/mol and forms small nanoparticles of a few tens of nm. Aqueous solutions containing 25 mg/mL oligomeric carrier, dissolved up to 0.5 mg/mL of drug. The oligomers exhibited a 10-fold better loading capacity compared to monomers and formed nanoparticles with a size in the 20–60 nm range after drug loading. All carriers with or without CLZ are not cytotoxic in the VERO cell line model up to 1 μ M, while CLZ alone is highly cytotoxic at the same concentration. The drug encapsulated or not has IC₅₀ values below 100 nM against *S. epidermidis* and clinical isolates of *S.*

epidermidis, some displaying MDR (**Figure 12**). So, noticeably, the selectivity index significantly increased for CLZ/carrier systems compared to the drug alone. These results open new opportunities for the clinical application of this antibiotic.

Figure 12. Solubilization of CLZ with SBE-EPI-p β CyD in water and improved selectivity index for the encapsulated drug.¹³⁴

Thomsen *et al.*, exploited two-photon excitation laser scanning fluorescence microscopy to study Rhodamine B labelled EPI-p β CyD penetration in bacterial biofilms evaluating the impact of the polymer charge.⁶⁶ Neutral Rho-EPI-p β CyD, anionic Rho-SBE-EPI-p β CyD polymer, and cationic Rho-QA-EPI-p β CyD were investigated. These polymers were applied to mature *Staphylococcus epidermidis* biofilms, a clinically relevant Gram-positive bacterium. Spatially resolved 3D visualization and spectral analysis demonstrated the better ability of the positively charged polymer to penetrate the biofilm (**Figure 13**).

Figure 13. Two-photon excitation microscopy data of *S. epidermidis* biofilms (72 h growth) treated with SYTO9 after incubation with Rho-QA-EPI-p β CyD (10 mg/mL in PBS for 15 min); left panel shows a 3D volume of the biofilm corresponding to 424x424x z μ m, ($40 < z < 100$ μ m, $\Delta z = 1$ μ m); right panel shows the emission spectra collected at different z -levels; The 453–549 nm emission corresponds to the SYTO9 stain, and the 562–718 nm emission to Rho-QA-EPI-p β CyD. Reproduced from ref. 66 with permission from Elsevier.

4.3 Other therapeutic agents

Skiba *et al.* proposed the encapsulation in pCyDs of Cyclosporine A (CsA, Table 5), a drug able to suppress various T-lymphocyte functions.⁷⁰ The poor water solubility of CsA is a major hurdle for its absorption into the blood stream, which leads to low bioavailability and thus lower efficacy. The innovative CsA drug delivery system contains CsA in spherical amorphous solid dispersion (SASD) which is embedded in a mixed α CyD and β CyD polymer obtained using citric acid (CTR- $\alpha\beta$ CyD), as a multifunctional amorphous carrier. The formulation showed that CsA was molecularly dispersed in CTR- $\alpha\beta$ CyDs in an amorphous form, as was confirmed by physicochemical characterization

studies. Interestingly, the peptide secondary structure, and thus, the drug activity was not impacted by the preparation of SASD. The *in vitro* CsA release profile kinetics was almost identical to the commercially available product Neoral®. The pharmacokinetic parameters of CsA from the spherical spray-dried dispersion formulation was demonstrated in a “rat” animal model and compared with Neoral®. Importantly, the pharmacokinetic parameters were improved by extending the time of maximum blood concentration from 2 to 3 hrs after the oral administration in rats, and eventually preventing the enterohepatic circulation. All these results clearly demonstrate the improved pharmacokinetic parameters and enhanced bioavailability of CsA in the CTR- $\alpha\beta$ CyD drug delivery system.

Li *et al.* proposed cationic β CyD oligomers obtained upon reaction of β CyD with EPI and choline chloride (CC-EPI- β CD) for the encapsulation of Naproxen (Table 5), a non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID). In spite of the very low MW the oligomers were able to increase Naproxen solubility in water with two orders of magnitude.⁶³

Monti *et al.* explored the use of EPI- β CyD for the encapsulation of artemisinin (Table 5), a highly effective drug for the treatment of malaria that suffers from water insolubility. They evidenced the ability of this polymer to encapsulate the drug inside cavities of the polymer NP where the drug experiences an alcoholic environment.¹³⁵

Trotta *et al.* have proposed α CyD for the delivery of oxygen in treatment of ischemias and in cardiovascular disease.⁷³ Indeed, already in 1956 Cramer and Henglein reported that cyclodextrins are able to complex gases in their hydrophobic cavity.¹³⁶ Trotta *et al.* developed an α CyD-based nanocarrier being the CyD with the smallest cavity to host molecular oxygen and ascertained its capability to reduce cell mortality during hypoxia and reoxygenation (H/R) *in vitro* protocols. The polymer with MW of 26 000 g/mol was obtained by reacting α CyD with pyromellitic dianhydride (PMDA) and was able to store and release molecular oxygen *in vitro*. H9c2, a cardiomyoblast cell line, was exposed to normoxic or hypoxic conditions. The formulation, applied before hypoxia, induced a significant reduction in cell mortality (in a range of 15% to 30%) when compared to samples devoid of oxygen. Moreover, their application at the beginning of reoxygenation induced a considerable reduction in cell death (12% to 20%).

Mazzaglia *et al.* proposed a polymeric CyD nanoassembly for the treatment of inflammation in osteoarticular diseases (**Figure 14**). They prepared nanoassemblies on EPI-amino- β CyD loaded with the non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug diclofenac (DCF, Table 5) and a fluorescent probe (adamantyl-Rhodamine conjugate, Ada-Rhod). The inclusion of DCF inside the CyD cavity helps reducing its gastrointestinal mucosal toxicity and improves the solubility of the drug, enhancing its bioavailability in the site of action and anti-inflammatory effect. The DCF release kinetics were investigated in medium mimicking the physiological conditions to ensure control over time and efficacy. Biological experiments evidenced the efficient cellular internalization of the assembly without significant cytotoxicity in primary human bone marrow-derived mesenchymal stromal cells as well as the ability to significantly suppressed IL-1 β production, revealing the anti-inflammatory properties of these nanoassemblies.¹³⁷

Figure 14: Sketch of nanoassemblies preparation using cationic EPI-amino-p β CyD. Reproduced from ref. 137 published under a Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license.

Ebselen (EB, Table 5), a lipophilic, organo-selenium compound has promising anti-HIV and anti-fungal activity. A rapidly soluble and non-cytotoxic vaginal film of EB was prepared with a dual purpose of treating vulvovaginal candidiasis and pre-exposure prophylactic activity against HIV. EB/EPI-p β CyD /Soluplus[®] (1:10:10) ternary complex (E β polySol) showed 200-fold enhancement in aqueous solubility of EB and no degradation of EB in thermogravimetry analysis. E β polySol film with tensile strength of 33 ± 2 N/cm² disintegrated within 30 sec, presented instant drug release with no apparent precipitation in simulated vaginal fluid. E β polySol film showed MIC of 20 μ M against *Candida* species and IC₅₀ of 0.71 μ M against HIV.¹³⁸

We conclude this part of the review with some comments on the use of the CyD polymers for the delivery of nucleic acids (NA). A large number of examples are nowadays available on the use of CyDs for NA delivery systems. An important number deals with monomeric polycationic CyDs grafted or not to polymers like PLA, PLGA, and polyethyleneimine or other materials. The electrostatic interaction of the polycationic CyD-containing system with NA is exploited to obtain NPs upon self-assembly processes with the ultimate goal to protect the NA from degradation and favor its entry in cells.^{139 140} Self-assembly of CyD-containing systems for NA delivery has further been improved exploiting a supramolecular approach based on the inclusion in the CyD cavity of specific ligands such as adamantyl and ferrocenyl groups and azobenzene grafted to a second component of the NA delivery system. Another popular category of CyD-based NA delivery systems is based on monomeric amphiphilic CyDs modified with lipophilic groups on one rim and charged functionalities on the opposite rim that self-assemble to form water soluble NPs. In the presence of NA electrostatically driven self-assembly is exploited to prepare NA loaded NPs with the CyDs protecting the NA from enzymatic degradation.¹⁴¹ Some of them are endowed with very promising behavior for cellular NA delivery. We further refer the reader to a very recent review by Xu *et al.* to have an overview on the CyD-based systems studied for nucleic acid delivery.¹⁴⁰ Differently, pCyDs reported up to now have been rarely exploited for nucleic acid delivery thus leaving a lot of space

for further investigation of these promising class of polymers. One example is represented by a linear cationic p β CyD obtained from the reaction of a diamino β CyD monomer with a diimide comonomer, forming polyplexes with nucleic acids and transfecting cultured cells.⁷⁷ The number of methylene units in the diimide comonomer is crucial for the NA transfection efficiency.

5. Light-activated therapeutic systems

An important amount of research on pCyDs has dealt with the development of light-responsive systems for the implementation of light-triggered treatments of various diseases. The main application fields of this part of R&D concerned the treatment of antibiotic infections and cancer. During the last decades we assisted a rise of interest in light-based therapies based on reactive oxygen and nitrogen species (ROS and RNS, respectively) as therapeutic species.¹⁴² Photochemically produced ROS and RNS are not susceptible to the development of multidrug resistance (MDR) and their production and action is confined to the irradiation site. Most interestingly, they can be produced upon light excitation of suitable light-responsive agents with precise spatiotemporal control. In addition, recent technological advances in lasers and fiber-optic tools are further facilitating the development of light-based treatments and an innovative category of clinical solutions. State-of-the-art technical advances in interstitial and intra-operative light delivery approaches, such as those used in the clinic in photodynamic therapy (PDT) protocols, allow the use of light-activated therapies for the treatment of a wide range of solid tumors, including breast, brain, lung, colon, ovarian, pancreas, and prostate.¹⁴³ These advances will likely be accompanied by personalized dosing and treatment schedule. In this context, pCyDs are a highly versatile platform to combine light-responsive therapeutic agents with classical drugs in a single supramolecular assembly thanks to their ability to load various compounds contemporarily.

Figure 15. Sketch of a photoactivable gel with three selected functional components: EPI-p β CyD, a hydrophobically modified dextran and a nitric oxide (NO) donor bearing an adamantyl appendage.¹⁴⁴

One of the first examples is reported by S. Sortino in 2013.¹⁴⁴ They reported on the preparation of a photoactivable gel platform by a simple “green” technology, taking advantage of the hydrophobic interactions between three selected functional components: an EPI-p β CyD, a hydrophobically modified dextran and a nitric oxide (NO) donor bearing an adamantyl appendage for light-activated NO release (**Figure 15**). The selected NO donor based on a nitroaniline moiety is known for its ability to produce NO radicals upon excitation with blue light.¹⁴⁵ The formation of the assembly is based on the inclusion of dextran alkyl side chains and the adamantane moiety of the NO donor in the β CyD cavities of the polymer. The multivalent character of the interactions between all components and the insolubility of the NO donor in an aqueous medium ensure the stability of the hydrogel and the total lack of leaching of the photoactive component from the gel network under physiological

conditions. The photochemical properties of the NO donor are well preserved in the gel matrix as demonstrated by the controlled release of NO through blue visible light excitation and its transfer to a protein such as myoglobin. The utility of this light-activated NO releasing platform is demonstrated in effective and strictly light-dependent bactericidal activity against the Gram-negative *Escherichia coli* bacterial colony suspension.

A very similar system based on EPI-p β CyD and hydrophobically modified dextran was reported in 2015 containing a bichromophoric molecular conjugate designed for light-activated NO release with an anthracenyl moiety as fluorescent reporter of the NO production (compound **3** in Figure 17).¹⁴⁶ In the gel excitation with blue light at 450 nm provoked NO release from the nitroaniline unit and contemporary activation of the blue anthracenyl fluorescence as the electron transfer quenching mechanism in the original conjugate is interrupted in the photoproduct. The NO radical can leach out of the gel to attack the targeted biological substrate transforming the gel in a light-activated source of the biologically relevant NO radical.

Figure 16. Sketch of a NP achieved upon self-assembly of EPI-p β CyD, zinc phthalocyanine as red emitting $^1\text{O}_2$ PS and the tailored molecular conjugate, as green emitting NO donor. Confocal images exploiting PS and NO donor fluorescence; panel A-B: NO and $^1\text{O}_2$ production profile exciting at 405 and 532 nm, respectively; panel C: dark and light ($\lambda_{\text{irr}}=400\text{-}800$ nm, 20 minutes) toxicity of melanoma cells treated with PS (a), NO donor (b) and both (c). Reproduced from ref. 147 with permission from the Royal Society of Chemistry.

The same authors also presented a photoactivable nanoplatforam for multimodal light-activated cancer therapy. The system exhibits (i) simultaneous visible light-triggered production of $^1\text{O}_2$ and NO and, as a consequence, (ii) amplified cancer cell mortality due to synergistic bimodality and (iii) dual-color fluorescence allowing its localization in cells. This nanoplatforam has been achieved upon self-assembly of (i) the EPI-p β CyD as carrier, (ii) the zinc phthalocyanine as $^1\text{O}_2$ photosensitizer (PS) emitting red fluorescence and (iii) the tailored NO donor conjugated to a nitrobenzofurazan as green emitter (**Figure 16**).¹⁴⁷ The system was tested on a melanoma cell line. Remarkable photodynamic inactivation induced by the NPs containing both the photoactive components compared to the performance of the NPs loaded with a single component provided clear-cut evidence of a bimodal photoinactivation mechanism killing neoplastic cells, in which NO and $^1\text{O}_2$ both played a key role. This example was the first proof-of-principle in which a $^1\text{O}_2$ photosensitizer and a NO photodonor acting simultaneously can be independently visualized using fluorescence microscopy, merging dual imaging capacity with dual photodynamic potential in one single nanostructure. This system was

also tested for its phototoxicity on human squamous carcinoma cells. Synergic phototoxicity was reported for the $^1\text{O}_2$ PS and NO donor.¹⁴⁸ Two-photon excitation (TPE) fluorescence at 840 nm allowed to visualize the assembly in human ex vivo skin samples as deep as 25 μm .

The same components have been used to prepare a hydrogel adding a dextran polymer modified with hydrophobic alkyl side chains.¹⁴⁹ The water insoluble co-entrapped species show excellent stability in the gel, which does not require any protective coating or shell to prevent the premature leaching. In the gel both $^1\text{O}_2$ sensitizer and NO donor maintained their activity upon stimulation with red and blue light, respectively. Noteworthy, conservation of the photobehavior of the independent components after their confinement in a restricted space is not trivial, as self-quenching of excited states often occurs between light-responsive agents in close proximity. It was the first example of a hydrogel showing dual-color fluorescence and bimodal photodynamic action and represents an intriguing model system for fluorescence-guided phototherapeutic applications.

In order to circumvent the disadvantage of the use of blue light in vivo the authors explored also two-photon excitation (TPE) phenomena to build multimodal systems. They prepared a TPE responsive, biocompatible nanoassembly for light-triggered NO release, based on EPI-p β CyD NPs encapsulating a molecular conjugate of the NO donor conjugated to anthracene (compound **3** in **Figure 17**).¹⁵⁰ TPE using NIR 700 nm laser light was applied to trigger *and* monitor the photorelease of NO: upon light-activated NO uncaging a fluorescent co-product was obtained acting as a TPE fluorescent reporter of the concomitant NO release from the nanoassembly. The system was tested on skin carcinoma cells killed upon TPE excitation after treatment with the assembly. It was the first example of a light-activated NO releasing nanoparticles capable of the nearly instantaneous quantification of such an important bioactive agent by two-photon fluorescence in living cells.

Figure 17. A green emitting EPI-p β CyD polymer loading the red emitting $^1\text{O}_2$ photosensitizer, Zn Phthalocyanine, and the blue emitting anthracene-based NO donor. Reproduced from ref. 151 with permission from Wiley.

In 2019 the authors reported a nanoassembly for the simultaneous generation of $^1\text{O}_2$ and NO and exhibiting three-color fluorescent signals, which allows the localization in cancer cells of the nanocarrier and its multiple cargoes by TPE at a single wavelength of 740 nm (Figure 17).¹⁵¹ The nanoassembly, of about 30 nm in diameter, was made of a green emitting fluorescein-labelled EPI- β CyD polymer co-encapsulating the red emitting singlet oxygen ($^1\text{O}_2$) photosensitizer Zn phthalocyanine and the blue emitting anthracene-based nitric oxide (NO) donor, cited above. All components can be simultaneously excited with two-photons using near-infrared light at 740 nm and despite their close proximity, behave as independent units. This allows for their *in vitro* visualization in carcinoma cancer cells, due to their distinct green, red, and blue fluorescence, and for the production of both cytotoxic $^1\text{O}_2$ and biofunctional NO.

Malanga *et al.* reported also on a light-activated system where the components are covalently linked to EPI- β CyD. In a one-step synthesis they prepared the polymer starting from a mixture of native β CyDs and two β CyD monomers covalently linked to either fluorescein or the NO donor, with EPI as crosslinking agent for the polycondensation reaction. The system offers a smart solution for the risk of premature loss of the loading present in non-covalent assemblies while it releases the NO radical upon irradiation at 405 nm and can be traced by means of the fluorescein green emission.¹⁵²

Finally, Mazzaglia *et al.* developed a fabric based on polypropylene fibers used as platform to be coated with β CyD polymers obtained from reaction of H β CyD with citric acid (CTR-pHP β CyD).¹⁵³ The CyD cavities acted as host for 5,10,15,20-tetrakis(4-sulfonatophenyl)-21H,23H-porphine (TPPS), a known photosensitizer of $^1\text{O}_2$. Chemical composition, morphology and photophysical properties were investigated. The whole system was tested as light-activated antibiotic device against *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 29213 and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ATCC 27853. The textile has efficacy against *S. Aureus* and can be implemented as covering or implants for treatment of infections.

6. Future Perspectives

From the scientific point of view a large amount of data are nowadays available on pCyDs as therapeutic agents and delivery tools. Nevertheless, up to now the above discussed polymers have not yet found a practical application in medicine. Looking for patents on the Espacenet website (updated on Feb 22, 2022), inserting “cyclodextrin AND polymer” in the fields “Title, abstract and names”, we found 1341 patents. Adding the term “delivery” we restrict to 62 patents, covering the 1994-2021 time span, with very few of them dealing with CyD polymers obtained with the procedures described in the first part of this review. Most of them deal with drug delivery system with CyDs grafted to a polymer such as PEG, chitosan, etc. One interesting patent entitled “Pharmaceutical composition for preventing or treating Arteriosclerosis containing cyclodextrin polymer as active ingredient” concerns the use of p β CyDs as intrinsic therapeutic agent for iv administration able to accumulate in the atherosclerotic plaques without causing hearing loss even if added at high concentration.¹⁵⁴ Another patent “Methods for administering nucleic acid-based therapeutics” concerns DNA delivery and relates to methods for administering nucleic acid-based therapeutics to treat a disease or disorder in a patient. In the patent embodiments, the nucleic acid-based therapeutic is an siRNA that is part of a composition comprising a linear cyclodextrin polymer.¹⁵⁵ Overall, also the low number of patent applications of CyD-based polymers affords a

clue that several questions still need an answer in view of their translation to the clinics as therapeutic agents and/or delivery system. Nevertheless, compared to other CyD-based composite systems and several other types of nanoparticles for therapeutic applications they represent several huge advantages first of all at the level of preparation.

The majority of the pCyDs cited in the first part are prepared following a polycondensation procedure in water and also some functionalization schemes can be achieved in the same solvent which represents a very appealing feature for sustainable development of new drug carriers or therapeutics. Moreover, the polycondensation procedure requires a very low number of reagents with accessible costs keeping the synthesis cheap and the starting materials are enzymatically produced (pharma grade β CyD \approx 150 €/kg). As already discussed, more biocompatible crosslinkers might be used, but still the first-choice agent remains EPI because of its versatility, easy-handling and low cost (25 €/kg), even though the compound is considered as probable human carcinogen. The preparation of these polymeric compounds is a standardized process at laboratory-scale and batch-to-batch reproducibility as well as the in-depth characterization of these derivatives has been largely achieved. However, these compounds are not yet prepared either under GLP or GMP conditions. The EPI-pCyDs are nowadays commercially available as fine chemicals produced in 100 g scale. The upscaling has not reached the kg scale because there has been no demand for large quantities yet. Importantly, actually feasible technology transfer of the currently available process to a specialized contract manufacturing organization would overcome easily the quantity issues. In this context, the preparation of engineering batches up to 20 kg of pCyDs would be mandatory before switching to dedicated facilities able to operate under GMP conditions, and technology is mature thus not precluding by any means the process implementation. Definitely, the only final obstacle is the high cost needed to make large-scale production operational and conform to GMP standards, including the QA/QC systems that allow and guarantee the correct life-cycle of manufactures. Conviction that this strategy is feasible is reinforced by the fact that this goal has already been reached for some monomeric CyDs that have found implementation in various drug formulations.

A further impetus to the implementation of the pCyDs in nanomedicine as therapeutics and/or vehicle for drugs and therapeutic/diagnostic agents comes from their different behavior compared to the corresponding monomers and in most cases their performance is superior. Overall, the improved aqueous solubility of the polymers compared to the native CyDs and the synergistic/cooperative effect of multiple CyDs units composing the construct has allowed to reach much higher dissolved drug concentrations in fluidic media compatible with *in vivo* conditions. Noticeably, several cases have been reported showing that combination therapy is feasible with these polymers able to encapsulate different types of therapeutic agents simultaneously, an elusive goal with the monomeric CyDs. These findings are of utmost importance in an era where MDR is spreading in the treatment of cancer as well as microbial infections compromising the output of conventional therapies. An aspect still to be better explored is the target specificity of the polymeric system, loaded or not. Modification of the CyDs with a targeting ligand is expected to be straightforward being available several synthetic routes to obtain functionalized CyDs.¹⁵⁶

Though green low-cost synthetic procedures and upscaling to large production quantities are feasible for pCyDs, their translation to the clinics as drug delivery systems implies much more. A question that deserves further investigation concerns the premature leakage of the cargo. This

problem does not always present as some applications do not require systemic administration but can be performed through local treatment as in the case of long infections, skin diseases, etc. It has already been proven that some of the cargo-loaded polymers are compatible for *in situ* pulmonary application with microsyringe systems. Where local application is not an option and systemic administration is required, the retention of the cargo becomes a crucial point. Some authors addressed this topic by mixing pCyDs with other polymers such as the hydrophobic dextrans to form more stable NPs. Others are exploring different approaches. An interesting example is the layer-by-layer assembly of p β CyD on solid lipid nanoparticles (SLN) of Compritol 888 ATO described by Amiel *et al.*¹⁵⁷ The negatively charged SLN core was successfully coated with positively charged p β CyD to obtain one layer SLN. Two layers SLN were produced by sequential deposition on the SLN of positively charged p β CyD bearing trimethyl ammonium and negatively charged p β CyD with sulfate groups. The coating process was monitored by means of particle size, size distribution, zeta potential, drug encapsulation, drug release patterns, and *in vitro* cell viability. This hierarchical core-corona structured lipid nanoparticles may provide advantages such as controllable particle size, surface charge modification, increased physical and chemical stability, prolonged circulation time and enhanced cellular interaction. The layer-by-layer coating strategy can afford a new drug delivery platform compatible with several administration routes.

Translation to the clinics also implies the requirement for sterile products. Some works have already examined this aspect studying different sterilization procedures. It will be necessary to evaluate carefully the correct timing of the sterilization phase that can occur at two stages. It is possible to use an autoclave for the final polymeric product to achieve class C/D sterile products. The same approach can be used for the loaded polymers but in that case a careful assessment of the production of by-products during autoclavation needs to be performed during the process of formulation development.

Being new entities, the described polymers obtained upon polycondensation need to be approved by Drug and Food agencies before being considered for practical biomedical applications, the focus of this review. None of them has reached this goal so far. This requires a full toxicologic screening, with high cost and up to now no pharma companies have assumed this task. In this context, once a polymer becomes FDA approved, we envisage the possibility to use it for the treatment of various diseases with already known drugs presenting administration issues without the necessity to present each time a full dossier for approval thus making the procedure easier. In this context various food and drug agencies recommend nowadays to adopt a Quality-by-Design (QbD) approach for new drug development.⁵² The latter represents a systematic approach to drug development that begins with predefined objectives and emphasizes product and process understanding and process control, based on sound science and quality risk management. These QbD elements all together eventually facilitate process capability and continual improvement. Also the systems presented in this review would draw benefit from a change in paradigm adopting the QbD approach.

7. Conclusions

In this review we collected the scientific data now available for polymeric CyDs as tools for biomedical applications based mostly on their high aqueous solubility and enhanced solubilizing effects; the empowered encapsulating properties deriving from the cooperative/synergic action of multiple CD units constituting the polymers generate a unique and flexible asset for the pharma

formulation development. Their synthetic versatility as well as the established green synthetic protocols at accessible costs give them a huge advantage over other nanocarriers. Being biocompatible and biodegradable, they arouse little concern from the environmental point of view. Their potential for clinical applications both as carriers and as bioactive substances is widely illustrated in this review. What's missing is the last mile to clinics that demands the contribution from pharma industry and clinical end-users as well as investments. As their monomeric models have reached the clinics, we are confident that also the polymers can cover this last mile.

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9. Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

10. Keywords

combination therapy, cyclodextrin polymers, nanomedicine, PDT

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